

Conflict Management Styles of Faculty and Staff of a State University in Northern Philippines

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ABSTRACT: The study explores the Conflict Management Styles (CMS) of faculty and staff and relationship of the CMS with their demographic profiles with an aim to develop a possible training program in Conflict Management. The participants were 26 faculty and 14 staff. Data were gathered using survey, interview and FGD. The instrument used is the Thomas-Killman CMS Inventory. The instrument yielded a CVI of 0.91 and a Cronbach Alpha of 0.95 which show that the validity and reliability of the instrument is very high. The data were analyzed by means of the descriptive statistics, the Z-test for independent sample means to determine the ratio of proportion of difference between the conflict management styles as perceived by the respondents; and the Chi square to determine any relationship between conflict management styles and demographic profiles of respondents. Results of the study reveal that the faculty and staff use different CMS. The dominant conflict management style for the faculty is avoiding and for the staff is compromising. It also shows that the faculty with administrative positions and some staff use combinations of the CMS like compromising-collaborating. The demographic profiles of the faculty and staff do not influence their conflict management styles. The study concludes that existing practices and strategies of faculty and staff in handling conflict needs enhancement on appropriate and effective conflict management styles. Thus, a possible training program on Conflict Management Styles was developed and proposed for implementation.

KEY WORDS: Conflict, conflict management, conflict management styles, faculty, staff

INTRODUCTION

Conflict is a natural part (Vokic & Sontor, 2010) and normal aspect of the life of people with different goals in an organization. Conflict is manifested when antagonism, harsh words, hostility and indifference exist between and among individuals in an organization or institution. It occurs every day in a workplace whenever objectives, values or purposes of different individuals or group are not compatible with those of colleagues (Lee, 2008) and those people obstruct each other to achieve personal objectives (George and Jones, 2006). Because

conflict is an unavoidable part of an organization (Adeyemi, 2009) that makes it one of the primary phenomena in an organization (Chaturangi & Padmasiri, 2014) that necessitates proper attention from management and leadership point of views.

Even though conflict is a common part of the human existence, many individuals do not possess the competencies needed to resolve conflicts effectively. Morgan (2012) believes that handling conflict is a logical perspective and a set of competencies used by individuals and groups of people to look at conflict in a better perspective and to dispense with any conflict situation in their lives. In this light, the acquisition of conflict management skills will empower every person to be responsible for their own conflicts and to resolve those conflicts.

Iglesias and Vallejo (2012) believe unsuccessful conflict management is a primary cause of stressful work environment, power play, employee dissatisfaction. Therefore, all members of an organization need to possess sufficient knowledge and skills in conflict management because implementing a functional conflict resolution style is essentially needed in many professions (Barsky, 2007 in Schroeder, 2014) and institutions.

Conflict is an indispensable dynamic in human relations (Mitchelle, 2006). People learn about rights and duties and individuals use the knowledge gain from education to interact with other people in a culturally diverse work place (Fahal Al Sabah, 2015), particularly in getting or not getting along with other human beings. To meet the emerging norm in conflict management, Duncan, et al (2011) emphasize the importance of conflict resolution training in the preparation and success of school administrators. The training involves teachers, students, parents, and school board members.

In the local context, Philippine Normal University North Luzon (PNU NL) as an institution like any other agency encounters conflict along administrative and academic sides. Issues on promotion, evaluation, incentives and human relation are some administrative issues to contend with. While there are existing conflict management styles practiced by administrators, the need for better and effective conflict management is still desired by concerned individuals. Managing conflicts in the school usually falls on school administrators, teachers and staff. Everybody can benefit greatly by understanding that conflict is something that does not go away unless it is resolved. Hence, identifying appropriate conflict management styles and planning a relevant training program is necessary. From this perspective, it appears there is a lot of work being done and still to be done with respect to assessing conflict and conflict management strategies but the factors affecting the choice of an individual regarding conflict management style still need to be studied and explored, and the present study is an attempt to fill-in the gap.

This study is conducted to describe the conflict management strategies of the faculty, and staff of the university and explore strategies that would enhance their conflict management skills. And lastly, from the possible result of the study, a training program on conflict management can possibly be developed.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Conflict and Causes of Conflict

Conflict may be described as a struggle or competition that occurs in the workplace among groups and individuals with differing needs, ideas, beliefs, values, or goals (The Foundation Coalition, 2003) that causes serious disagreement or argument (Schramm-Nielsen, 2002) in satisfying their needs and interests (George, et. al. 2013).

Conflict presently continues to be a factor in all walks of professions and organizations, personal and academic life. When we talk of schools, we talk of faculty, other employees, and students as well as other stakeholders. There in their midst unexpectedly and unavoidably, conflict happens.

A cause of conflict according to Aquino (2013) in Calora, (2020) is that the low commitment of teachers obstructs good working environment and may veer away from the educational purpose of the school. The result has a negative effect to teachers' performance and to the school as well. This scenario gives rise to a serious conflict between school administrators and teachers. Gwanyo, Dickson and Tanatu (2020) aptly sum up that conflict is a worldwide organization process viewed by individuals and groups as irksome, while there some people who believe conflict improves effectiveness of individual or group contribution in the organization as long as it is properly managed taking into consideration the nature, quality and amount of resources at the organization's distribution.

2. Conflict Management

Conflict management is the use of resolution and stimulation techniques to attain the targeted level of conflict that sustains peaceful coexistence and understanding in achieving common objective which sustains effectiveness (Gwanyo, Dickson and Tanatu, 2020), and restore order and stability (Ramani and Zhimin, 2010).

Conflict Management programs should include the basic philosophy and skills of conflict management (Morgan, 2012) and some form of a problem-solving process models such as negotiation, mediation, or consensus decision-making (Fisher and Ury, 1983 in Cutts, 2016).

According to Kenneth W. Thomas and Ralph H. Kilmann (1974 in Islamodlu, et. al. 2017), there are five conflict management styles that a manager will follow: accommodating, avoiding, collaborating, competing, and compromising. Even though all five conflict management styles are utilized within organizations, researches give evidence that the most frequently used conflict handling style among world population is compromising (Hignite, Margavio & Chin., 2002; Pinto & Ferrer, 2002), as people are inclined to seek approval and tend to compromise. Another, according to Unver (2002 in Islamoglu et. al., 2008) both subordinates and superiors most often employ collaborating styles of conflict management. In another study, the most dominant conflict management style of faculty in dealing with conflicts with supervisor, peers and students was collaborating. Only few of the respondents preferred accommodating and competing styles in dealing with conflicts towards their supervisor, peers and

students; while avoiding was used in dealing conflicts with peers. Respondents never compromised in handling conflicts with supervisors, peers, and students (Rambuyon & Domondon, 2021).

A study by Mabunga and Mabunga (2019) reveals that the conflict management styles of officials from selected State Universities and Colleges in the Philippines include compromiser, accommodator, controller, avoider and collaborator as the dominant CMS. The study of Illescas and Perez (2020) shows that collaborating is evident and the dominating conflict management style among elementary school heads while they also claimed that avoiding is an effective conflict management style. Calora (2020) says the most serious problem in terms of conflict management is the absence of camaraderie and teamwork among teachers. To resolve this type of organizational conflict, understanding one another is the most recommended solution

Shanka and Thuo (2017) list the major conflict management strategies use by school leader. These include building leadership skills, obeying rules and regulations. Accepting change, wise distribution of resources, participation in decision making, giving opportunities for training, and understanding individual differences and roles. Further, techniques used in case of disputes are discussing, punishing, forcing, compromising, avoiding, and ignoring. The study concludes that school leaders need to identify the sources of conflicts and establish a mechanism where staff can express their concerns. One thing more, leaders have to enhance their leadership skills, accept change, include and provide opportunities for staff professional growth. And school leaders should look for means to acquire and generate funds.

3. Factors that affect conflict management style

Several factors affect the way an individual deal with conflict. According to Curtis (2012) , these are temperament, culture, context, relationship, values, experiences and upbringing. The way that a person see the conflict comes from who s/he is as well as the relationship s/he has with the other person. For instance, if s/he has a positive relationship with the other person, s/he may agree to a friendly resolution but if their relationship is not good, the other person may interpret everything negatively, thus an amicable settlement may not be possible. The kind of relationship with others definitely affects the way one communicates, whether positive or negative. Other factors that influence how people make a response to conflict are gender, self-concept, expectations, situation, position/power, practice, determining the best mode, communication, and life experiences.

According to Judith Musyoki (2013) the administrators' preferred accommodative CMS because it is highly cooperative. Avoidance conflict management was the least used by the administrators. It is recommended that the administrators should understand that gender, working experience, and academic qualification are associated with different conflict management styles. Good choice of conflict management style by the administrators will improve performance and establish strong relationship within the university. Another study shows that school administrators practice the accommodating conflict management style since as leaders they are with greater authority to decide on how a conflict will be dealt with appropriately (Gumiran, 2021).

Williams (2015) found in her study that effective management of conflict can produce effective teamwork and leadership, higher morale, increased productivity, satisfied customers, and satisfied employees. On the other hand, ineffective conflict management styles in the workplace can result to low levels of job satisfaction, resulting in high levels of turnover. The more a lower level supervisor uses the compromising conflict management style, the more the job satisfaction level decreases. Finally, the results show that conflict management style avoiding, compromising, dominating, integrating, and obliging used by an individual have no significant relationship with their level of job satisfaction.

Ghaffar, Zaman, and Naz (2012) examine the most preferred styles of the public and private secondary schools' principals in District Charsadda (KPK). The findings reveal that the most preferred conflict management styles are compromising and accommodating. Teachers perceived that the administrators do not or never attempt to use avoiding in dealing with conflict. However, the conclusion is that all the principals should adopt the best style as the situation demands. It is recommended that principals should be given proper conflict management training on resolving interpersonal problems.

Moreover, the practice of appropriate conflict management styles promote creativity of employees, sharpen capability to learning, enhance psychological well-being, improve commitment with organization, and strengthen teamwork (Schulz-Hardt, Mojzisch, &

Vogelgesang, 2008). However, when disputes are not managed well, workers experience stress, poor decision making and judgment (Pruitt & Kugler, 2014).

Studies show that cultural diversity, work environment and experience and interdependence of people in the organization cause conflict. These mentioned issues are influenced by other demographic factors like gender (Green, Brewer, Mitchell and Weber, 2002), age, education, position, marital status, and parenthood.

Several research results show that women were found to use the avoiding style more than men, while men were more likely to use the compromising style more than women (Mckenna and Richardson, 1995 in Islamodlu, Birsal, and Boru, 2008), while Rahim (1983) found that women were inclined to use cooperative styles like obliging and integrating more than men. Meanwhile, the study of Mokhtarpour, & Mokhtarpour (2013) reveal a statistically significant difference between gender and the use of the fivefold approach in the domination style. The principals frequently use the compromise mode followed by collaboration and accommodation, domination and avoidance. There was a significant relationship between the principals' level of income and the use of collaboration and accommodation styles. The study of Hasani, K., Boroujerdi, S.S., Sheikhesmaelli, S. and Aeni, T. (2014) reveals that women prefer problem-solving when handling conflict and men prefer forcing more than women regardless of roles in the organization.

Studies reveal that age is a factor of organizational conflict. Havenga (2006) discloses that younger individuals are more inclined to use the dominating conflict handling style while older people choose compromising (Pinto & Ferrer, 2002), and prefer collaborating (Cetin & Hacifazlioglu, 2004). It was observed that age is an important variable affecting conflict handling styles. As academics and teachers get older, they are more flexible and constructive when they talk with their peers. They use more often collaboration styles.

Smith and Magill (2009 in Hasani, et.al., 2018) pointed out that education might be a driving force of dispute by fueling grievances, stereotypes, xenophobia and other antagonisms. Although education can also contribute to conflict resolution and peace building. Education may cause some sort of misunderstanding in a society but it also creates a peaceful resolution in the end (Dupuy, 2009).

Experience is very important in managing conflict in the school. According to Ehinola (2012) less-experienced school leaders tend to use force or command, authority and traditional strategies in dealing with conflicts in their respective schools, while the experienced principals are inclined to use agreement, mediation and bargaining appeal to subordinate.

Practice of conflict handling strategies differs across hierarchical levels. Individuals in the upper organizational positions are found to be greater on the competitive and collaborating styles while people with lower status prefer and report higher use of avoiding, accommodating and compromising (Brewer, Mitchell & Weber, 2002)

Studies acknowledge that gender predicts dominating conflict handling styles and marital status would possibly predict the use of avoiding style (Goel, 2012). According to Riaz, K.R., Jamal, W. and Jan, F.A. (2016), even though there is no significant relationship between marital status and conflict handling style, it is a common belief that married people and those with children are compelled to use more cooperative conflict handling approach. Individuals who have children demonstrate significantly higher use of avoiding, accommodating and compromising styles than those with no children. The avoiding, accommodating and compromising styles of resolving conflict are characterized by low or moderate concern for self, exactly the way people with younger children, should think and behave. One more thing, married people prefer to practice accommodating conflict handling style than unmarried in order to build and live a happy married life. In order to do so, people often have to set aside their own interests, and place their family's interests above their own. In terms of religion, Christians and Hindus prefer the collaborating style; work experience in the compromising styles; and educational qualification shows significant difference on the competing style (Chathurangi and Padmasiri. (2014).

The reviewed literature reveal an immense study on the reality and importance of conflict, conflict management, conflict management styles and the impact of demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, religion, culture, tenure, position, and education to conflict management styles of the people of an organization whether business or academic. The huge relevant information which are found among research articles suggest how conflict can be turned into constructive or functional by means of choosing appropriate conflict management styles and using effectively combinations of the certain styles. In the advent of very

high interest in conflict management, the influence of demographic characteristics on conflict management techniques is still under exploration. The investigations conducted in studying the relationship between conflict management styles and demographic variables have involved mostly gender, age, civil status and position. The demographic factors ethnicity and performance rating are open for further investigation. The relationship between these demographic variables- performance rating and ethnicity and conflict management styles has not extensively been tested while considered to be important to improve personal and organizational relations. In this study, the connection between conflict management styles and demographic profiles such as age, gender, civil status, education, number of children, ethnicity, years in service, rank, administrative position, and performance will be explored in order to come up with a possible training program on Conflict Management Styles for the faculty and staff of the Philippine Normal University North Luzon.

Statement of the Problems

The purpose of the study is to describe the conflict management styles of the faculty and staff of the Philippine Normal University North Luzon, and to develop a possible conflict management style training for them.

Specifically, the study will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of faculty and staff in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age?
 - 1.2 Gender?
 - 1.3 Civil Status?
 - 1.4 Ethnicity?
 - 1.5 Number of children?
 - 1.6 Educational qualification?
 - 1.7 Years in service?
 - 1.8 Rank?
 - 1.9 Administrative position?
 - 1.10 Performance?
2. What are the conflict management styles of faculty and staff of PNU NL as perceived by themselves?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and conflict management styles of faculty and staff?
4. What possible Conflict Management Training Program can be developed based on the results?

Hypotheses

There is no significant relationship between the demographic profiles and perceived conflict management styles of faculty and staff.

Conceptual Framework

Conflict happens instantly or gradually. In an organization, having an effective conflict management style is important for leaders and individuals and it is essential that they recognize how conflict can be constructive or destructive depending on the approach that is taken during the conflict (Boulter, et.al. 2001).

Conflict may arise anytime within an interaction between and among individuals. The context is the emphasis on relationships. Therefore, whether the cause is lack of common listening skill or the complex ideas and actions that stem from a person's spiritual principles (Goldberg, 2009), individuals cannot live successful life without the knowledge and practice of a good conflict management style. For this reason, conflict management skills are very important for an individual to perform effectively in whatever capacity in an institution.

This study is anchored on Conflict Management Styles by Kilmann and Thomas (1975, Updated 2002), Conflict prevention and competence (Fisher and Ury, 1983), and Intergroup Contact Theory (Allport, 1954)

The model of conflict management styles initially presented by Blake and Mouton (1964) and further developed by Kilmann and Thomas (1975) and Rahim (1983) presents five conflict handling strategies (Rahim, 1992; Rahim and Magner, 1995). The styles for managing conflict differ based on two basic dimensions: "concern for self" and "concern for others." The **integrating/collaborating** style refers to cooperating and joining forces with the other party involved in the conflict. It involves working together between parties. The **obliging/accommodating** style refers to being helpful and being considerate of the welfare of others. It tends to smooth over differences and focus on how the parties can come to agreement. The **dominating/competing** style refers

to being in charge and in control of the other party involved in the conflict. It is described as forcing one’s beliefs and ideas to the extent of sacrificing other people’s expense. The **avoiding** style involves withdrawing and keeping away from the conflict situation. The **compromising** style refers to give-and –take principle in search for solution beneficial to both parties involved..

Fisher and Ury’s Four Principles of Negotiations (1983 in Cutts, 2016) identified four principles of effective negotiation- 1) Separate the people from the problem, 2) Focus on interests not position, 3) Invent options for mutual gains, and 4) Insist on using objective criteria upon which to base agreement. The principles aver that understanding the difference in culture and personality traits influence how people negotiate. When these differences are considered, an important step is done towards a better understanding of the negotiation process that may lead to more integrative mediations in the future.

In universities, faculty and staff encounter conflicts that are task related and relationship- based which need amicable settlement. In order to do, both faculty and staff need to acquire appropriate and effective strategies in handling interpersonal conflicts for academic departments to function smoothly (Cetin & Hacifazlioglu, 2010). Consequently, when faculty, and staff learn to be very objective in managing conflict, harmony in relations increase, productivity and outstanding performance take place , thus achieving the goal of the organization is smooth and easy.

The Intergroup Contact theory of Allport (1954) cited in Ives, Alama, Oikonomidoy, and Obenchain (2016) posits that interactions between individuals in different social groups occur between the groups under conducive circumstances is a worthy strategy to reduce intergroup hostility and prejudice between majority and minority group members. This means that contact contributes positively in reducing prejudice and promoting more positive intergroup attitudes. Obviously, when people from varied cultural backgrounds work together, conflicts naturally occur and due to that fact, good and effecient conflict management strategies are needed. Hence, the possible impact of effective conflict handling is significant to policy work.

In the process, the teaching and non-teaching employee’s social and professional behavior will serve as model on how these employees resolve conflict among them. There are strategies on how to handle and resolve conflicts that will enable administrators, faculty and staff formulate their own conflict management system designed according to their respective needs . Therefore, faculty and staff by constant positive intergroup contact may learn and practice using appropriate and effective conflict management styles (McKibben, 2017).

Ideally, all administrators, faculty, students, school personnel, parents, and stakeholders working together should undergo conflict management skills training. The more people are equipped with conflict management skills, the more the skills will be valued, modeled, encouraged, and practiced by people in conflict situations. Consequently, conflicts may be prevented or minimized and harmony and high productivity in the workplace may prevail. To achieve this goal, there is a need to come up with a conflict management training program (Mabunga, et. al. 2014, McKibben, 2017).

Figure 2. Paradigm of the study

Scope and delimitation

The study encompasses the description of the conflict management styles and selected demographics of the faculty and staff of the Philippine Normal University North Luzon, Alicia, Isabela. It also describes the relationship between their CMS and demographics and proposes a training program for employees and student leaders. The research does not focus on the implication of the study on the policy making aspect of the institutions regarding conflict resolution or conflict management.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The descriptive correlational research design was used in this study as it covers the relationship between administrators, faculty, staff and students' conflict management styles and demographic profiles. *Descriptive research* gives an accurate picture of characteristics of a specific individual, situation or a group. Meanwhile, *correlation* is a statistical measure of the expanse two variables are related (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2012).

The Respondents

The 26 faculty and 14 administrative staff were purposively selected respondents in the study.

Data Gathering Instruments

The Conflict Management Styles Questionnaire. The *Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument (TKI)* by Thomas and Kilmann (1975, Updated 2002) was adapted and used by the researcher. The Survey questionnaire is made of two parts. The first part is on the demographic profiles of respondents and the second part is the Conflict Management Styles.

Interview. Semi-structured interviews with selected faculty and staff were done to gather information not covered by the survey questionnaire.

Focus Group Discussion. FGD was conducted with selected respondents to validate quantitative data and to gather supplementary input on CMS from faculty-administrators/heads, faculty and staff.

Statistical Treatment

To make an accurate analysis of the quantitative data, the following statistical treatments were utilized: the descriptive statistics-the measure of central tendency such as mean (\bar{X}), frequency distribution (N), and percentage (%) to determine: (a) conflict management styles of administrators, faculty, staff and students as perceived by themselves; the Z-test for independent sample means to determine the ratio of proportion of difference between the conflict management styles as perceived by the respondents; and the Chi square to determine any relationship between conflict management styles and demographic profiles of respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows that there are more employed female (14) than male (12) faculty members. With regard to age and status, 14 respondents fall within age range of 50 years and below and 17 respondents are married or widow while 9 of the respondents are single. There are 15 Ilokano respondents and 11 non-Ilokano. It can be observed that 15 respondents have 2 or more children while 11 respondents have one or no child. The highest education attained by the respondents is doctorate with a frequency of 15 while 11 respondents have master's degree. For the number of years in service and years rendered at PNU, 12 respondents have rendered service for 20 years and above while 13 respondents have rendered service at PNU for 20 years and below.

Moreover, 18 respondents have a rank of associate professor or professor and 8 respondents have a rank of assistant professor or instructor. The faculty respondents with administrative position of dean or associate dean are 14 and 12 respondents have no designation. As for the respondents' performance, 12 respondents attained good or better while 5 respondents have been recognized as best.

Table 3.1 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Faculty Grouped According to Demographics

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Male			PhD/EdD	15	57.7
Female	12	46.2	MA	11	42.3
	14	53.8	Bachelor's Degree	-	-
			College Level	-	-
			(Not indicated)	-	-
Total	26	100	Total	26	100
Age			Years in Service		
20 – 29	1	3.8	1 – 10	4	15.4
30 – 39	4	15.4	11 – 20	5	19.2
40 – 49	9	34.6	21 – 30	7	26.9
50 – 59	7	26.9	31 – 40	4	15.4
60 and above	3	11.5	41 – 50	1	3.8
(Not indicated)	2	7.7	(Not indicated)	5	19.2
Total	26	100	Total	26	100
Civil Status			Years in PNU		
Single	9	34.6	1 – 10	7	26.9
Married	16	61.5	11 – 20	6	23.1
Widow	1	3.8	21 – 30	8	30.8
			31 – 40	2	7.7
			(Not indicated)	3	11.5
Total	26	100	Total	26	100
Ethnicity			Rank		
Ilocano	15	57.7	Professor	5	19.2
Ibanag	3	11.5	Associate Professor	13	50.0
Tagalog	4	15.4	Assistant Professor	4	15.4
Yogad	1	3.8	Instructor	4	15.4
Malaweg	1	3.8			
Itawes	2	7.7			
Ifugao	-	-			
Gaddang	-	-			
(Not indicated)	-	-			
Total	26	100	Total	26	100
Number of Children			Administrative Position		
0	9	34.6	Dean	1	3.8
1	2	7.7	Associate Dean	3	11.5
2	5	19.2	Head/In-charge	10	38.5
3	9	34.6	None	12	46.2
4	1	3.8	Staff	-	-
5	-	-			
9	-	-			
Total	26	100		26	100

Years in Service			Performance		
1 – 10	4	15.4	Best Better Good (Not indicated)	5 10 2 9	19.2 38.5 7.7 34.6
11 – 20	5	19.2			
21 – 30	7	26.9			
31 – 40	4	15.4			
41 – 50	1	3.8			
(Not indicated)	5	19.2			
Total	26	100	Total	26	100

Demographic Profile of the Staff

Table 2 shows the profile of staff according to gender, age, civil status, ethnicity, number of children, educational qualification, years in government service, years in PNU NL, administrative position, and performance. The rank is not included in the profile since no one indicated his/her rank i.e. Administrative Officer I, II or III.

The data show that ten (10) male and four (4) female staff respondents are employed. With regard to age and status, respondents belong to age 40 above and below. Eleven (11) respondents are married while 3 are single and one is widow. There are seven (7) Ilokano respondents and four (4) non-Ilokano staff.

It can be drawn from the data that 10 respondents have 2 or more children while three respondents have one child and one is childless. The highest education attained by the respondents is college level or graduate with a frequency of 9 while 3 respondents have master’s degree. For the number of years in the service and years rendered at PNU, 6 respondents have rendered service for 20 years and below while 5 respondents have rendered service at PNU for 20 years and above.

The 14 staff respondents have the same rank and the same performance.

Table 3.2 Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Staff Grouped According to Demographics

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Male Female	10 4	71.4 28.6	PhD/EdD	0	0
			MA	3	21.4
			Bachelor’s Degree	7	50.0
			College Level	2	14.3
			(Not indicated)	2	14.3
Total	14	100	Total	14	100
Age			Years in Service		
20 – 29	4	28.6	1 – 10	2	14.3
30 – 39	3	21.4	11 – 20	4	28.6
40 – 49	2	14.3	21 – 30	5	35.7
50 – 59	4	28.6	31 – 40	0	0
60 and above	1	7.1	41 – 50	0	0
(Not indicated)	-	-	(Not indicated)	3	21.4
Total	14	100	Total	14	100
Civil Status			Years in PNU		
Single	3	21.4	1 – 10	4	28.6
Married	10	71.4	11 – 20	4	28.6
Widow	1	7.1	21 – 30	5	35.7
			31 – 40	0	0
			(Not indicated)	1	7.1
Total	14	100	Total	14	100

Ethnicity			Administrative Position		
Ilocano	7	50.0			
Ibanag	-	-			
Tagalog	-	-	Dean	-	-
Yogad	3	21.4	Associate Dean	-	-
Malaweg	-	-	Head/In-charge	-	-
Itawes	-	-	None	-	-
Ifugao	1	7.1	Staff	14	100
Gaddang	1	7.1			
(Not indicated)	2	14.3			
Total	14	100	Total	14	100
Number of Children			Performance		
0	3	21.4			
1	1	7.1	Best	0	0
2	5	35.7	Better	9	64.3
3	2	14.3	Good	0	0
4	0	0	(Not indicated)	5	35.7
5	2	14.3			
9	1	7.1			
Total	14	100	Total	14	100

Conflict and Causes of Conflict

To find out whether conflict is present in the University, an interview was conducted.

The common causes of conflict according to the faculty are communication (miscommunication, poor communication) disagreement, competition, lack of cooperation, opposing personal views/philosophies, indifference, laziness, poor work habits, poor leadership skills, factionalism, inequity, faculty loading and number of preparations, misunderstanding of goals and expectations. Conflict is present among faculty of the PNU NL as explicitly disclosed and those conflicts spring from varied reasons identified by Chan and Chen (2010) such as poor communication, poor task management, being self-centered, different values, lack of sense of responsibility and initiative. This finding further supports the theories that conflict is natural (Vokic & Sontor, 2010) and cannot be avoided (Adeyemi, 2009) in any organization between and among the people therein with different objectives (Lee, 2008, George and Jones, 2006).

Below are the causes of conflict according to Faculty

1. *Communication gap and being closed minded (F17, F19, F26)*
Poor communication (F18)
2. *Disagreement of views about some issues; competition in one's work (F21)*
3. *subjective competition for position (F19)*
lack of cooperation when a person does not get what she/he wants (F19)
4. *different philosophies and views about reality. (F20)*
5. *...pride, subjective competition for position, status, recognition, etc., selfishness (F21)*
6. *Misunderstanding and lack or inadequacy of explanation on things/issues. (F22)*
7. *Differences in opinions or principles (F23)*
8. *Poor work habits, Laziness of employee/employer. Differences in personality. Poor leadership. Misunderstanding of goals and expectations (F18)*
9. *When both parties/persons failed to see each other's point/s of view (F23)*
10. *Poor communication. (F25)*

11. *Misunderstanding, different values of people, factionalism, inequity, faculty loading & number of preparations, selfishness, greediness. (F19, F26)*

Table 3 shows the relationship between the demographic profile and conflict management style of the faculty. As seen on the data, male respondents make use of compromising and avoiding strategies while female respondents use avoiding in resolving conflicts. This result negates the finding of Vokic and Sontor (2010) that female employees practice significantly more accommodating and compromising management strategies than men.

As to age, respondents whose age fall under 50 resolve conflicts by compromising while 50 and above respondents resolve conflicts by avoiding. Both married or widow and single respondents prefer avoiding conflicts.

In addition, Ilocano respondents prefer avoiding to resolve conflicts while non-Ilocano respondents choose collaborating, compromising, and avoiding to settle interpersonal conflicts.

For faculty respondents with none or one child, they prefer avoiding the conflict while respondents with two or more children are inclined to compromising when settling conflicts. In addition, faculty members with a rank of associate professor or professor would resolve the conflict by means of avoiding and faculty members with a rank of assistant professor chose compromising to settle the conflict. With regard to respondents with administrative post, they both prefer avoiding the conflict at hand.

Faculty respondents who are best performers opt to resolve the conflict by collaborating and compromising while faculty respondents whose performance is good or better opt to resolve the conflict by avoiding the situation.

On compromising conflict management styles, faculty members explain:

"I have to consider the personality/individuality of the other person. Reconsider each other's opinion, then compromise." (Faculty 9)

"Listen to one's concern. Be objective in decision making by looking the pros and cons, talk to the person and explain the reasons behind the decisions" (Faculty 3).

"I always say . . . you will have your chance next time. But be sure to prove you are worth the trust." (Faculty with Administrative Post 1).

On collaborating conflict management styles, faculty members opine:

"Try to talk to him in a nice and democratic ways and explain why you need to work together." (Faculty 11)

"Seek other's help/advice in working out a solution." (Faculty 8)

Interestingly, two faculty with administrative assignments point out the following:

"I make it sure that policies and communication are clear, consistent, and the reasons for decisions is transparent. However, the way I handle conflict depends on the nature of the conflict and the personality of the persons involved." (FA1)

"I have to ensure that all faculty and staff—not just department heads—are accountable for resolving conflict." (FA 2).

The above statements by the office and department heads on handling conflicts involving all employees show that contact and interactive accountability is necessary as theorized by the Intergroup Contact theory of Allport (1954 cited in Ives, et. al. (2016) that interchange between individuals in different social groups happen between the groups under conducive circumstances is a good strategy to reduce intergroup hostility and prejudice between majority and minority group members. Since conflict is unavoidable (Adeyemi, 2009) and one of the phenomena in an organization (Chaturangi & Padmasiri, 2014) it should be given proper attention from the management. The possible impact of effective conflict handling is significant to policy work. The sufficient knowledge and skills (Schroeder, 2014) on how to handle and resolve conflicts will enable administrators, faculty and staff formulate their own conflict management system designed according to their respective needs

As to the relationship of the faculty CMS with their demographic profiles, the result shows that age, gender, civil status, ethnicity, number of children, rank, administrative post, educational attainment, years in service, years in PNU, and performance have no significant relationship. This is inconsistent with the studies that conflict management styles is related to gender (Islamodlu, et. al, 2008; Rahim, 1983; Goel, 2012; Mokhtarpour & Mokhtarpour, 2013; Hasani, et. al., 2014); age (Havenga, 2006; Pinto & Ferrer, 2002; Cetin & Hacifazlioglu, 2004); experience or years in service (Ehinola, 2012); position or rank (Brewer, et al, 2002);

educational qualification (Chaturangi & Padmasiri, 2014). However, the result is similar to the studies of Riaz, et al (2016) that marital status has no significant relationship with conflict management styles.

As indicated in the table, the demographic profile of the respondents has no influence in their conflict management style. Implicitly for PNU faculty, their conflict management styles should not be limited to compromising and avoiding. Hence, it can be deduced that a possible training program for faculty on conflict management styles be developed and proposed.

Table 3. Relationship between the Demographic Profile and Conflict Management Style of the Faculty

Profile		CMS					Total	df	x ²	p value	Decision	Interpretation
		Competing	Collaborating	Compromising	Avoiding	Accommodating						
Gender	Male	2	2	4	4	0	12	4	4.27	.371	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Female	0	2	4	6	2	14					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Age	Below 50	1	2	6	4	1	14	4	2.51	.642	Accept Ho	Not significant
	50 & above	0	2	2	5	1	10					
	Total	1	4	8	9	2	24					
Civil Status	Single	2	1	1	4	1	9	4	6.01	.199	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Married/Widow	0	3	7	6	1	17					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Ethnicity	Ilocano	1	1	5	7	1	15	4	2.54	.637	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Others	1	3	3	3	1	11					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
No. of Children	0 – 1	2	1	2	5	1	11	4	4.49	.344	Accept Ho	Not significant
	2 or more	0	3	6	5	1	15					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Educational Qualification	PhD/EdD	0	3	4	7	1	15	4	4.08	.395	Accept Ho	Not significant
	MA/MS	2	1	4	3	1	11					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Years in Service	20 & below	1	2	2	3	1	9	4	1.77	.777	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Above 20	0	2	4	5	1	12					
	Total	1	4	6	8	2	21					
Years in PNU	20 & below	1	3	3	4	2	13	4	3.93	.416	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Above 20	0	1	4	5	0	10					
	Total	1	4	7	9	2	23					
Rank	Assoc Prof/Prof.	0	4	5	8	1	18	4	7.34	.119	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Asst. Prof/Instr	2	0	3	2	1	8					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Admin. Post	None	0	2	4	5	1	12	4	1.86	.762	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Dean/Assoc Dean	2	2	4	5	1	14					
	Total	2	4	8	10	2	26					
Performance	Best	0	2	2	0	1	5	4	6.91	.141	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Good/Better	2	1	5	4	0	12					
	Total	2	3	7	4	1	17					

Causes of Conflict and Conflict Management Styles of the Staff

In the interview conducted with the staff, the causes of conflicts include the superior’s authoritative/dictatorial style, inefficiency of the office head, indifference, apathy, lack of communication, favoritism, irresponsibility and laziness of other employees, lack of support for staff development, and promotion. Admittedly, conflict occurs when an individual feels a lot of frustration because of the actions of his/her coworkers or heads. Since conflict is an indispensable dynamic in human relations (Mitchelle, 2006), people must learn to interact with other people in a culturally diverse work place (Fahad Al Sabah, 2015).

Below are some reasons of conflict expressed by the staff:

1. *When treatment by the boss is not good. One is always wrong, they are always right. . . . does not listen to explanation) (Staff 1)*
2. *“competition in one’s work, favoritism” (Staff 2)*
3. *“... inefficiency of office head, lack of communication, authoritarian” (Staff 3)*
“(lack of support to subordinate’s professional growth” (Staff 7)
4. *“ when one does not accept responsibility and pass the work to others” (Staff 8)*
5. *so many tasks or requests to be done at once, then gets scolded when not accomplished at instructed time. (Staff 9)*

Staff Demographic Profiles and Conflict Management Styles

Table 4 shows the relationship between the demographic profile and conflict management style of the staff. Both male and female respondents whose age is below forty and 40 above prefer to resolve a conflict through compromising strategies. Respondents whose status is single prefer competing while married or widow respondents prefer compromising in resolving a conflict. Moreover, Ilocano respondents prefer competing, compromising, and accommodating while non-Ilocano respondents choose compromising to settle interpersonal conflicts. For respondents with none or one child, they prefer competing while respondents with two or more children are inclined to compromising when settling conflicts. Staff respondents, considering their educational attainment, years in service and years rendered at PNU, prefer to resolve the conflict by compromising with their co-workers.

As regards to the relationship of Staff CMS with their demographic profiles, the result shows gender, age, civil status, ethnicity, number of children, years in service, educational attainment, and performance have no significant relationship.

As indicated in the table, the demographic profile of the respondents has no influence on their conflict management style. However, it is quite surprising to note that no one among the staff uses collaborating as conflict management style. Managing conflict cooperatively help build the ideal positive share to team performance in a multi-cultural environments while a high degree of team coordination also exists (Tabassi,et al, 2017). To meet the emerging norm in conflict management (Duncan, et. al., 2011) emphasize the importance of conflict resolution training for school administrators and teachers. This implies a need to enhance the knowledge of the staff on other CMS. It is therefore imperative that a training on conflict management styles for PNU Staff development be developed.

Table 3.4 Relationship between the Demographic Profile and Conflict Management Style of the Staff

Profile		CMS				Total	df	x ²	p value	Decision	Interpretation
		Compe-ting	Compro-mising	Avoid-ing	Accomo-dating						
Gender	Male	3	4	1	2	10	3	.53	.913	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Female	1	2	0	1						
	Total	4	6	1	3						
Age	Below 40	2	3	1	1	7	3	1.33	.721	Accept Ho	Not significant
	40 & above	2	3	0	2						
	Total	4	6	1	3						
Civil Status	Single	2	0	0	1	3	3	4.10	.251	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Married/Widow	2	6	1	2						
	Total	4	6	1	3						

Ethnicity	Ilocano	2	2	1	2	7	3	2.95	.400	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Others	2	3	0	0	5					
	Total	4	5	1	2	12					
No. of Children	0 – 1	2	1	0	1	4	3	1.75	.626	Accept Ho	Not significant
	2 or more	2	5	1	2	10					
	Total	4	6	1	3	14					
Educational Qualification	MA/MS Coll.	1	2	0	0	3	3	.89	.828	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Level/Grad	3	4	1	1	9					
	Total	4	6	1	1	12					
Years in Service	20 & below	0	4	1	1	6	3	3.61	.307	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Above 20	2	2	0	1	5					
	Total	2	6	1	2	11					
Years in PNU	20 & below	2	4	1	1	8	3	1.03	.794	Accept Ho	Not significant
	Above 20	2	2	0	1	5					
	Total	4	6	1	2	13					

(Note: Some do not total 14 because of the missing data. Also, rank and performance are not included in the test because all respondents have only one and the same response)

Table 5 reveals that faculty respondents are inclined to make use of **avoiding and compromising** while Staff respondents, on the other hand, make use of **compromising and accommodating** strategies. It can be noted that there are faculty and staff who use combinations of two of the five different approaches. Based on the data, it can also be deduced that each social group has limited CMS that implies a need for them to acquire further knowledge on conflict management for a broader perspective. In conclusion, there is a need to enhance the knowledge and practice of faculty and staff on Conflict Management Styles because a good choice of Conflict Management Styles by the faculty and staff will improve work and build strong relationship within the university (Musyoki, 2013). There is a need to make a choice of good conflict management styles irrespective of gender, age, civil status, ethnicity, educational qualification, number of children, years in the service, rank and position, salary and performance level because at the end of the day, superiors and subordinates, faculty and staff should choose and practice the best style appropriate to the demand of the situation (Ghaffar, et. al. 2012). Additionally, when individuals understand culture differences and personality traits as the major reasons why people negotiate differently, they begin to make important step towards a better understanding of the negotiation process that may result to more integrative mediations in the future. The predominant conflict management styles of faculty and staff which are avoiding and compromising though somehow useful do not ensure collaboration, harmony or good working relationship between and among the respective social group. Therefore, in order to be equipped with knowledge and practice on good choice of conflict management styles, a training program is needed.

Table 5. Summary of conflict management styles of the respondents

Conflict Management Style	Faculty		Staff		Total	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Competing	1	3.8	3	21.4	4	10.00
Collaborating	1	3.8	0	0	1	2.50
Compromising	5	19.2	4	28.6	9	22.50
Avoiding	10	38.5	1	7.1	11	27.50
Accommodating	2	7.7	3	21.4	5	12.50
Combination	7	26.9	3	21.4	10	25.00
Total	26	100	14	100	40	100

D. Proposed Training on Conflict Management Styles for Faculty and Staff

The more people possess conflict management skills, the more opportunity the skills will be valued, modeled, encouraged, and used by individuals in conflict situations. To achieve this goal, there is a need to come up with a conflict management training program (Mabunga et.al. 2014, McKibben, 2017).

The Possible Conflict Management Styles Training for Faculty and Staff

Objectives	Topics	Strategies	Time Allotment
1. To equip faculty and staff with the knowledge, values, attitudes, and behaviors required to allow them to perform their tasks effectively (Wikipedia,2001, cited in Ogena 2014). 2. To understand the awareness, motivation, beliefs, attitudes, socio-cultural differences and development of collaboration among university employees and students.	1.1 Conflict Management Styles: Definition, Concepts, and Characteristics	Lectures/Discussion Brainstorming	2 hours
	1.2 Conflict Management Styles of Faculty, Staff and Students in Retrospect: The Need for Training on Conflict Management Styles	Lecture-cum discussion	2 hours
	2.1 Conflict Management Styles and The Professional Code of Ethics	CMS Awareness Test (Adapted)	15 minutes
	2.2 Conflict Management Styles and Emotional Intelligence and Spiritual Intelligence	Lecture-cum discussion	2 hours
3. To clarify the concept of conflict and collaboration	Conflict Resolution: Ways of dealing with conflicts within a group	Self-analysis Techniques Lecture-cum discussion	1 hour
4. To strengthen leadership on problem-solving, negotiating skills, team-oriented attitude and social communication skills.	The Role of Human Resources The Role of University Officials The Role of Faculty The Role of Staff The Role of Students	Storytelling and problem-solving (Collaborative Activity)	2 hours
5. To develop the possible institutional mechanism for conflict management	The process of effective conflict management	Brainstorming Crafting PNU NL Conflict Management System	4 hours

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

The study confirms the theory that conflict is an inherent part in the life within the organization and its people. Its main source is the differences innate to every individual. When the differences in philosophies, beliefs, values, goals and motives surface, conflict arises.

The faculty, staff and student leaders have their own conflict management styles in managing conflicts. The dominant conflict management style for the faculty is avoiding and for the staff is compromising. The faculty with administrative positions and some staff uses combination of conflict management styles as situation dictates.

The demographic profiles of the faculty and staff have no significant relationship with their respective conflict management styles. Factors like gender, age, civil status, ethnicity, number of children, years in service, educational attainment, rank, administrative

position, and performance have no influence on their conflict management styles. However, the limited knowledge and practice on appropriate and effective conflict management styles calls for enhancement.

Lastly, a possible training program on Conflict Management for faculty and staff has been developed from the results of the study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the foregoing conclusions, it is recommended that the proposed training program on conflict management styles for faculty, staff and students be conducted and consequently PNU NL be able to develop an institutional conflict management system. For further research, a study on the effects of various conflict management strategies applied by faculty, staff and student leaders on performance (productivity for faculty and staff and academic performance for students) be undertaken.

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